

1 **Title**
2 Disaggregation of canopy photosynthesis among tree species in a mixed broadleaf forest
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41 **Abstract:**

42 Carbon dioxide sequestration from the atmosphere is commonly assessed using the eddy
43 covariance (EC) method. Its net flux signal can be decomposed into gross primary production
44 (GPP) and ecosystem respiration components, but these have seldom been tested against
45 independent methods. In addition, EC lacks the ability to partition carbon sequestration among
46 individual trees or species within mixed forests. Therefore, we compared GPP from EC to an
47 independent method based on sap flow and water-use efficiency, as measured by the tissue heat
48 balance method and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of phloem contents, respectively. The latter measurements were
49 conducted on individual trees throughout a growing season in a mixed broadleaf forest
50 dominated by three tree species, namely English oak, narrow-leaved ash, and common
51 hornbeam. In this context, we applied an alternative ecophysiological method aimed at
52 verifying the accuracy of a state-of-the-art EC system while also offering a solution to the
53 partitioning problem. We observed strong agreement in the ecosystem GPP estimates ($R^2 =$
54 $0.56; p < 0.0001$), with correlation being especially high and nearly on the 1:1 line in the period
55 before DOY 212 ($R^2 = 0.85; p < 0.0001$). Following this period, the estimates began to diverge.
56 Possible reasons for the divergence are discussed, focusing especially on phenology and the
57 limits of the isotopic data. English oak showed the highest per-tree daily photosynthetic rates
58 among tree species, but the smaller, more abundant common hornbeam contributed most to the
59 stand-level summation, especially early in the spring. These findings provide a rigorous test of
60 the methods and the species-level photosynthesis offers avenues for enhancing forest
61 management aimed at carbon sequestration.

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65 **1 Introduction**

66 Forests provide an important sink for atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂), a greenhouse
67 gas that contributes to ongoing climate change (Pan et al. 2011). Particularly important is
68 canopy photosynthesis, or gross primary production (GPP), which measures the total rate of
69 CO₂ uptake from the atmosphere. Ecosystem-scale CO₂ fluxes are generally measured using
70 the eddy covariance (EC) method (Baldocchi 2003, Aubinet et al. 2012). The key strength of
71 this method is that it integrates CO₂ fluxes over everything that happens below a horizontal
72 plane above the canopy (Baldocchi 2008). Consequently, its results can accurately assess the
73 net CO₂ balance of the whole ecosystem.

74 Despite its strengths, the EC method faces challenges in describing the component
75 fluxes occurring within the ecosystem (Wehr et al. 2016), as it typically involves using quasi-
76 mechanistic models to distinguish, e.g., GPP from ecosystem respiration (R_{eco}) (Reichstein et
77 al. 2005). Specifically, it is often assumed that GPP can be estimated from an asymptotic
78 relation with incoming radiation and that R_{eco} can be estimated from temperatures. If either of
79 these models is incorrect, both the GPP and the R_{eco} estimates will be inaccurate, and our
80 understanding of the ecosystem will be flawed. Measurements by the EC method are
81 sometimes compared to ground-based biometric measurements, including chamber
82 measurements of component flux and allometric measurements of component mass (Ryan
83 2023). Typically, the EC method reports lower R_{eco} while higher net annual C storage (i.e., net
84 ecosystem production) compared to biometric estimates (Campioli et al. 2016, Marshall et al.
85 2023). Another challenge, especially in forests, is that the elevated canopy and divergence in
86 stratification across the canopy partially block the passage of eddies from the air mass below
87 the canopy into the air mass above, termed decoupling (Thomas et al. 2013). This limits the
88 ability of the below-canopy CO₂ sources to contribute to measurements made above and is
89 especially pronounced in complex terrain (Jocher et al. 2020) and forests with diverse structure
90 (Paul-Limoges et al. 2017, Kowalska et al. 2022).

91 Moreover, EC cannot disaggregate the ecosystem fluxes among individual trees or
92 species within the ecosystem (cf. Kowalska *et al.*, 2020). Understanding the contribution of
93 each species to overall CO₂ sequestration is vital for effective forest management, especially
94 in the context of climate-change mitigation strategies (Campioli et al. 2015, Luysaert et al.
95 2018). Individual trees can vary greatly in their rates of photosynthesis, and hence their carbon
96 sequestration potential, due to differences in factors such as species, age, health status, and

97 environmental conditions (Bassow and Bazzaz 1997). Several studies have tried to understand
98 the relationship between EC derived photosynthesis (carbon source) and carbon allocation
99 (carbon sink), typically focusing only on aboveground woody biomass (Delpierre et al. 2016,
100 Krejza et al. 2022, Puchi et al. 2023). Although such studies can allocate wood growth among
101 species and over the season, they cannot provide species-specific rates of photosynthesis
102 because the proportion of photosynthesis used for wood growth is small and variable (e.g.,
103 Marshall et al., 2023). Therefore, a method that can accurately estimate the photosynthetic rates
104 of individual trees, and thereby their CO₂ sequestration potential, could greatly enhance our
105 ability to manage forests for carbon capture (Ameray et al. 2021).

106 We tested GPP estimates by EC against an independent, alternative ecophysiological
107 method (Hu et al. 2010, Klein et al. 2016). The ecophysiological method (ISO/SF) relies on
108 measurements of sap flow as a proxy of transpiration (Poyatos et al. 2021). When combined
109 with the atmospheric vapor pressure deficit, transpiration yields estimates of stomatal
110 conductance (Jones 2013). The method also relies on stable carbon isotope ratios ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) of
111 organic compounds dissolved in the phloem sap, which can be used to estimate intrinsic water-
112 use efficiency (iWUE), the ratio of CO₂ uptake to stomatal conductance. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of phloem
113 contents has proven useful for this purpose (Vernay et al. 2020, Schiestl-Aalto et al. 2021)
114 because they provide a weighted estimate of iWUE of recent gas-exchange based on all the
115 dissolved carbon transported through the phloem (Gimeno et al. 2021). Notably, both
116 measurements are made on tree stems, allowing for the disaggregation of the canopy flux down
117 to individual trees. The per-tree scale gives us the opportunity to assess the contributions of
118 different species and size classes to the canopy-scale GPP estimate derived from EC. Finally,
119 ISO/SF method can be applied to all types of forest ecosystems, including those in complex
120 terrain and with decoupling issues (Etzold et al. 2010, Jocher et al. 2017, 2020).

121 In previous studies, the ISO/SF method agreed well with EC in a boreal pine forest
122 (Vernay et al., 2020), but significantly underestimated GPP by EC in mixed forest of pines and
123 spruces (Vernay et al. 2024). Evidently, the Granier heat dissipation (GHD, Granier (1985))
124 method used for sap flow measurements in these studies worked well for pine, but not for
125 spruce (Vernay et al. 2024). The underestimates were likely due to problems with scaling
126 measurements to the whole stem (Steppe et al. 2010, Peters et al. 2018). Similar
127 underestimations by the GHD method have been previously reported in Aleppo pines (Klein et
128 al. 2016). Here we have applied an alternative sap flow method, namely the Tissue Heat

129 Balance (THB) method, which is thought to minimize scaling issues (Schulze et al. 1985,
130 Urban et al. 2012).

131 In this study, we compared methods in a mixed floodplain forest dominated by three
132 deciduous broadleaf tree species: English oak (*Quercus robur* L.), narrow-leaved ash (*Fraxinus*
133 *angustifolia* Vahl), and common hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus* L.), hereafter referred to as oak,
134 ash, and hornbeam respectively. Oak and ash have ring-porous wood and hornbeam has
135 diffuse-porous wood; both these are quite different from the tracheids of conifers that have
136 previously been studied. To our knowledge, this is the first study to test GPP estimates by the
137 two methods in a mixed broadleaf ecosystem and the first to use the THB method for sap flow.
138 Given the focus here on broadleaf species, we expected that the impact of leaf development on
139 photosynthesis would be crucial. Therefore, we provide detailed measurements of leaf
140 phenology to help explain photosynthesis dynamics in these species.

141 In summary, the objectives of the study were: (i) to compare GPP estimates from EC
142 techniques to independent estimates based on sap flow and phloem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ for the first time in a
143 diverse, deciduous mixed-broadleaf forest, (ii) to apply the THB method of estimating sap flow
144 for the first time to ISO/SF GPP estimation, and (iii) to partition canopy GPP among three
145 phenologically distinct species over the course of the growing season.

146 **2 Material and methods**

147 **2.1 Site description**

148 The Lanžhot site is a part of the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS, [www.icos-](http://www.icos-cp.eu/news-and-events/icoscapes/lanzhot)
149 [cp.eu/news-and-events/icoscapes/lanzhot](http://www.icos-cp.eu/news-and-events/icoscapes/lanzhot)) network, representing the hardwood floodplain
150 forests (Kowalska et al. 2020). It is located in the south-east part of Czech Republic
151 approximately 6 km north from of the confluence of the Morava and Dyje rivers (48° 40.090
152 N, 16° 56.780 E; 154 m asl). The long-term average annual precipitation from 1961–2017 is
153 around 497 mm, with a mean annual temperature of 9.7 °C. The average groundwater level
154 during 1966–2018 was -2.6 m (Szatniewska et al. 2022). The plot is on an alluvial plain and
155 the main soil types are Eutric Humic Fluvisol, Haplic Fluvisol, and Eutric Fluvisol with a
156 minimum soil depth of 60 cm (Acosta et al. 2017).

157 The experimental site, consisting of ~110 years old trees, is composed of typical hardwood
158 species representative for the region (Szatniewska et al. 2022). This forest is predominantly

159 composed of oak, ash, and hornbeam, with a range of other species contributing to the
160 biodiversity but having a negligible contribution to the stand's basal area (Table S1).

161 The average stand height is 27 m. Oak and ash create the main stand canopy and represent
162 dominant and co-dominant social classes, while hornbeam is primarily found under the main
163 canopy layer (Figs. S1 and S2). Despite its small size, hornbeam stems are the most numerous
164 tree species, followed by ash and oak (Table S1).

165 **2.2 Environmental data and leaf phenology observations**

166 Although microclimatic conditions on this site have been recorded since 2015, this study
167 focused specifically on data from 2021 (Fig. 1). Throughout this year, relative air humidity
168 (RH, %) and air temperature (T, °C) were recorded with calibrated EMS 33 sensors (EMS
169 Brno, Czech Republic), while precipitation (P, mm) was measured using a rain gauge 386C
170 (Met One Instruments, Grants Pass, OR, USA). Global incoming radiation (R_g , $W\ m^{-2}$) was
171 measured with a CNR4 (Kipp & Zonen, Delft, Netherlands) radiation sensor. Photosynthetic
172 Photon Flux Density (PPFD, $\mu mol\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$) was measured under the canopy with quantum EMS
173 12 (EMS Brno, Czech Republic) sensors. Atmospheric pressure (P_a , hPa) was recorded at 3 m
174 of height with a barometer PTB110 (Vaisala, Finland). The vapor pressure deficit (VPD; hPa)
175 was calculated from RH and T, by first determining the saturation vapor pressure, and then
176 calculating the difference between the actual and the saturation RH (Jones 2013). The soil water
177 content (SWC, %) was assessed at various soil depths - 5, 10, 20, 50, and 100 cm, in each of
178 the four cardinal directions around the plot center, using CS616l sensors (Campbell Scientific,
179 Inc., USA). All data were recorded every 30 s, with an averaging period of 30 min.

180 The atmospheric CO₂ concentration (C_a , ppm) and atmospheric $\delta^{13}C$ signature ($\delta^{13}C_a$, ‰; Fig.
181 S3) in 2021 were both collected from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
182 database using the nearest sample station at the Ochsenkopf in Germany (Thompson et al.
183 2009).

184 Leaf phenological observations were conducted on the dominant tree species at the study site
185 (Fig. 2). Observations were focused on seven oak trees, five ash trees, and six hornbeam trees,
186 each was chosen for proximity to the meteorological mast. Consistent observations were
187 carried out by the same person three times per week in the spring, and twice per week during
188 summer and autumn. Using binoculars, these observations were made from both the ground
189 and from the mast, primarily targeting the upper parts of the tree crowns. Using the
190 methodology previously described in Nezval *et al.* (2020), leaf phenophases were classified

191 into several stages: bud break (BB), 10 to 100% foliage formation (FF), fully developed leaf
192 area (FDLA), 10% leaf color change (LC10), 10% leaf fall (LF10), 100% leaf color change
193 (LC100), and 100% leaf fall (LF100), with the latter observed only in ash trees.

194 **2.3 Eddy covariance GPP derivation**

195 The energy and matter fluxes at Lanžhot were determined by the Eddy covariance (EC)
196 method. The EC system was installed on the meteorological mast at 44 m above the ground. It
197 consisted of an ultrasonic anemometer (Gill Instruments, Hampshire, UK) for measuring the
198 3-dimensional wind components and sonic temperature, as well as an enclosed infrared gas
199 analyzer LI-7200 (LI-COR, Lincoln, NE, USA) for CO₂ and water vapor concentration
200 measurements. All measurements were taken at a frequency of 20 Hz.

201 A second identical system was installed under the canopy, positioned 3.5 m above the ground,
202 near the meteorological mast (Kowalska et al. 2022). The below-canopy data were used to
203 estimate the extent of canopy decoupling by investigating the relation of the standard deviation
204 of vertical wind (σ_w) between below and above canopy air masses. In the earlier study,
205 decoupling events occurred frequently but had little influence on annual net ecosystem CO₂
206 exchange estimates, meaning that our study site was relatively free of such errors. We did not
207 use the decoupling filter in our analysis because it tended to eliminate morning and evening
208 values. These values were necessary for accurate daily sums. Daily sums were necessary to
209 match the sap-flow data in the Iso/SF method (described below).

210 Vertical turbulent fluxes were computed by the EC method described previously by, e.g., Lee
211 *et al.* (2005) and Aubinet *et al.* (2012), with an averaging period of 30 minutes. All flux
212 calculations were performed with the EddyPro EC software (Fratini and Mauder 2014). The
213 accurate application of the EC method requires several corrections to be made on the calculated
214 covariance between the vertical wind component (w) and the quantity of interest, for instance,
215 CO₂ when considering CO₂ flux. A planar fit coordinate rotation, as detailed by Wilczak *et al.*
216 (2001), was employed to ensure the long-term average of the vertical wind measurements was
217 negligible, as well as to rotate the measurements into the main wind direction. Moreover,
218 corrections for potential flux losses in the high-frequency range, possibly due to path length
219 averaging or the spatial separation of the sonic measurement path and gas analyzer, were
220 applied following the procedure described in Ibrom *et al.* (2007).

221 The EC software also included a quality-flagging scheme testing the data for stationarity and
222 development of turbulence; it provided an overall quality flag combining the results of both

223 tests (Foken et al. 2005). Only flux data with best quality were used for further considerations.
224 We also applied a friction velocity (u^*) threshold on our flux data which ensured that the mixing
225 across the canopy was sufficient to measure representatively above the canopy.

226 Carbon flux partitioning and data gap filling were performed using R package REddyProc
227 (Wutzler et al. 2018). Gap-filling was conducted there via marginal distribution sampling
228 (Reichstein et al. 2005). Regarding the flux partitioning, we followed the “daytime” approach
229 as proposed by Lasslop *et al.* (2010). This approach uses night-time CO_2 flux to infer the
230 temperature sensitivity of R_{eco} but uses daytime data only to parameterize the light- and
231 temperature-driven models of GPP (hereafter GPP_{EC} ; $\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and R_{eco} , respectively
232 (Wohlfahrt and Galvagno 2017).

233 **2.4 Tree level transpiration and conductance**

234 Sap flow was measured in 5-7 healthy, undamaged trees of each species situated within the
235 footprint area of the EC system measurements. The sampled trees were selected to represent
236 the distribution of diameters at breast height across the forest (Fig. S2; Szatniewska et al.,
237 2022). The sap flow measurements were conducted using the THB method with internal
238 heating and sensing (Kučera et al. 1977, Čermák et al. 2004), which allowed approximation of
239 whole-tree water use or tree transpiration. The specific sensors employed were the EMS81
240 modules (EMS Brno, Czech Republic), which were installed at breast height of the trees (1.3
241 m), typically on the north side to avoid interference with phloem sampling. Contrary to other
242 methods, THB involves heating the xylem with an alternating electrical current passed between
243 a set of three flat stainless steel electrodes. A major advantage of this approach is that it
244 eliminates heat transfer between the heating element and the water-active xylem, significantly
245 reducing errors at higher sap flow rates (Tatarinov et al. 2005). Moreover, when the electrode
246 length adequately matches the expected sapwood depth, the measurements become almost
247 independent of the radial profile of sap flow rates. Consequently, we utilized shorter electrodes
248 for ring-porous species (oak and ash) and longer electrodes for the diffuse-porous species
249 (hornbeam), corresponding to the deeper sapwood typically found in diffuse-porous species.
250 Based on this assumption, the sensors provide sap flow values in kilograms per cm of stem
251 circumference at the cambium.

252 Sap flow data were recorded at two-minute intervals and stored as 10-minute averages. These
253 values were then further averaged to hourly intervals and expressed as specific sap flow (Q)
254 per unit of trunk circumference ($\text{kg h}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The Exponential Feedback Weighting method as

255 detailed by Kučera *et al.* (2020) was used to eliminate heat losses by establishing a baseline
256 (using 5-d period) from the night-time zero-flow values when there was no demand for
257 evaporation. Hourly Q values were further aggregated to daily sums per tree ($\text{kg day}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$).
258 Finally, to compute the sap flow for the entire tree ($Q_{\text{tree}}, \text{kg day}^{-1} \text{tree}^{-1}$), Q was multiplied by
259 the specific circumference of each individual tree, excluding the bark and phloem layers, the
260 thickness of which were measured during sensor installation (Fig. 2).

261 Crown conductance to H_2O vapour was then calculated using the following equation (Vernay
262 *et al.* 2020):

$$263 \quad g_{\text{tree}} = \frac{Q_{\text{tree}} \times 1000}{\frac{M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{\text{VPD}_D} Pa} \quad (1)$$

264 In Eq. (1), Q_{tree} is first converted from $\text{kg H}_2\text{O day}^{-1} \text{tree}^{-1}$ to $\text{mol H}_2\text{O day}^{-1} \text{tree}^{-1}$. VPD_D ,
265 representing the daytime vapor pressure deficit, was calculated using the periods when R_g
266 exceeded a threshold of 10 W m^{-2} to define 'daytime'. The resulting conductance values are
267 expressed in $\text{mol H}_2\text{O tree}^{-1} \text{day}^{-1}$, meaning that they integrate over all the leaves in the crown
268 of a given tree on a given day.

269 **2.5 Phloem isotopes, discrimination and ISO/SF GPP derivation**

270 We quantified the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of the solutes transported within the phloem tissue, represented
271 as $\delta^{13}\text{C}_p$, in per mil (‰). Phloem samples were collected biweekly from five trees of each
272 species, within the same trees used for sap flow measurements (Fig. S2), beginning on March
273 31 and ending on November 2, 2021, to encompass the entire photosynthetic period. A bark
274 punch, 9 mm in diameter, was used to extract a cylinder containing bark, phloem, cambium
275 and xylem. To minimize local disturbance, samples were taken from slightly different heights
276 on the trees at each sampling. After removing bark and xylem, a sample containing active
277 phloem was subsequently dropped into a 2 ml vial containing 1 ml of deionized water, allowing
278 time for exudation (approx. 5 h; Gessler *et al.* (2004)). The phloem sample was then removed
279 from the vial, and the exudates were frozen until the processing time.

280 To determine $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values, 150 μl of phloem exudates were transferred and dried in tin capsules
281 at 60°C for 12 h, following the method of Gessler *et al.* (2004), with minor modifications as
282 detailed in Vernay *et al.* (2020). For $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ measurements, the samples were combusted to CO_2
283 at 960°C using an elemental analyzer varioPYRO cube (Elementar Analysensysteme,
284 Germany). The stable isotopes in the resulting CO_2 were then determined by a continuous flow

285 isotope ratio mass spectrometer ISOPRIME100 (Isoprime, UK). Finally, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_p$ values were
 286 calculated as the deviation from the Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite (VPDB) standard using the
 287 formula,

$$288 \quad \delta^{13}\text{C}_p = [({}^{13}\text{C}/{}^{12}\text{C}_{\text{phloem}}) / ({}^{13}\text{C}/{}^{12}\text{C}_{\text{VPDB}}) - 1] \times 1000 \quad (2)$$

289 where $\delta^{13}\text{C}_p$ is the ratio of the heavy to light isotope (${}^{13}\text{C}/{}^{12}\text{C}$) in phloem sample.

290 The ${}^{13}\text{C}$ discrimination (Δ , ‰) was estimated by correcting the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_p$ values in phloem exudates
 291 for the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_a$ values at the time of photosynthesis. It was assumed that the phloem exudates
 292 were predominantly composed of recent photosynthetic carbohydrates (Klein et al. 2016,
 293 Vernay et al. 2020). The following equation was utilized for the calculations:

$$294 \quad \Delta = \frac{\delta^{13}\text{C}_a - \delta^{13}\text{C}_p}{1 + \frac{\delta^{13}\text{C}_p}{1000}} \quad (3)$$

295 The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_a$ data used for Δ calculations in Eq. 3 were obtained from the polynomial fit presented
 296 in Fig. S3. The ISO/SF method required the determination of daily values of Δ . Linear
 297 regression was used to model the data, excluding those values collected prior to full leaf foliage
 298 formation (shown in red in Fig. 3). This approach was based on the assumption that
 299 carbohydrates present before this stage are likely remnants of the previous year's
 300 photosynthates.

301 Subsequently, the ratio of the internal to ambient concentration of CO_2 ($C_i : C_a$) was derived
 302 from (Farquhar et al. 1982):

$$303 \quad C_i : C_a = (\Delta - a) / (b - a) \quad (4)$$

304 where a is the fractionation caused by the diffusion of CO_2 in air (4.4‰); b is the fractionation
 305 resulting from the active site of the Rubisco enzyme (27‰). Subsequently, a proxy for iWUE
 306 ($C_a - C_i$) was derived from:

$$307 \quad C_a - C_i = C_a \times (1 - C_i : C_a) \quad (5)$$

308 The net photosynthesis rate of individual trees/species ($A_{\text{ISO/SF}}$, $\text{g C day}^{-1} \text{ tree}^{-1}$) was then
 309 calculated as:

$$310 \quad A_{\text{ISO/SF}} = g_{\text{tree}} \times 0.625 \times (C_a - C_i) \times \frac{M_C}{10^6} \quad (6)$$

311 with 0.625 representing the ratio of the diffusivities of CO_2 to H_2O in air, and M_C , the molar
 312 mass of C (12 g mol^{-1}).

313 Finally, the rate of stand-scale photosynthesis ($GPP_{ISO/SF}$, $g\ C\ m^{-2}\ day^{-1}$) per species was
314 estimated by multiplying the average per-tree photosynthetic rate of each species by the
315 respective number of trees of each species per hectare (refer to Tab. S1 and Fig. 2).

316 **2.7 Statistics**

317 Given that the assumptions of homogeneity and normality were not met for the photosynthesis
318 rates among the species, the Kruskal-Wallis' test was employed to analyze variance and identify
319 differences across species. When significant differences were found, a post-hoc Dunn's test
320 was used for pairwise comparisons. To evaluate the agreement between the methods, we
321 employed linear regression for the analysis spanning the whole year. All statistical analyses in
322 this study were conducted with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The data analyses and
323 visualization were performed using R statistical software (ver. 4.2; R Core Team, Vienna,
324 Austria) and OriginPro software (OriginLab Corporation, Massachusetts, USA).

325 **3 Results**

326 **3.1 Microclimatic conditions**

327 In the study year, 2021, conditions were mostly normal. The average temperature was $10.4\ ^\circ C$
328 and total precipitation was 480 mm (Fig. 1). These values are marginally warmer (by $0.8\ ^\circ C$)
329 and drier (20 mm) than the long-term average (1961-2017). The only unusual weather was in
330 April and May, when it was $2\ ^\circ C$ colder than the long-term average. (Fig. 1a).

331

332 The daytime vapour pressure deficit (VPD_D) was consistently high from early June to mid-
333 August (Fig. 1b). Precipitation was relatively low in the first part of the year (January-May),
334 but SWC did not begin to fall until the end of May. The summertime fall in SWC was briefly
335 alleviated by abundant rainfall in mid-July and again in mid-August (Fig. 1d). However, after
336 this short relief, the SWC continued to fall until late September (Fig. 1c).

337 **3.2 Species-specific sap flow and leaf phenology**

338 Variations in vegetative leaf phenophases and sap flow patterns were observed among the
339 species within the study year (Fig. 2). In the spring, bud break (BB) and foliage formation (FF)
340 occurred first in hornbeam, subsequently in oak, and lastly in ash. A similar order was observed
341 in autumn, with leaf coloring (LC) occurring first in hornbeam, then oak, and finally in ash.
342 However, compared to the other two species, ash exhibited much more rapid leaf senescence.
343 Similarly, hornbeam initiated transpiration earliest, followed by oak and ash (Fig. 2). For

344 hornbeam, nearly two weeks passed between full leafout (FF100%) and the beginning of
345 transpiration, but oak and ash began to transpire as soon as they were fully leafed out (Fig. 2).
346 The delay in hornbeam occurred during a period when nighttime temperatures were still falling
347 nearly to 0 °C (Fig. 1). Hornbeam and ash achieved their maximum sap flow around DOY 170,
348 whereas oak's peak came slightly later, around DOY 215 (Fig. 2). Maximum flow rates were
349 similar in ash and hornbeam and somewhat higher in the oak. After the leaf area was fully
350 developed (FDLA), sap flow rates began to decrease across all species, with a particularly rapid
351 decline following the first appearance of leaf coloring (LC 10%); this decline was especially
352 noticeable in ash.

353 **3.3 Isotope composition and discrimination**

354 Seasonal variation in the isotopic composition of phloem contents ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_p$) differed among
355 species. The discrimination data, which were corrected for seasonal variation in the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of
356 atmospheric CO_2 , showed a distinct decrease in all species four to five weeks after full leafout.
357 Disregarding this early period, a distinct negative trend was observed in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_p$ (Fig. 3)
358 concurrent with a significant positive trend in discrimination (Δ ; see inset in Fig. 3). The three
359 species displayed similar Δ trends, with statistical analysis confirming no significant difference
360 in the slopes among species ($F = 0.40$, $p = 0.672$). Despite similar seasonal trends,
361 discrimination values varied among species, with hornbeam at $19.7\text{‰} \pm 0.25$ SEM significantly
362 different from the other tree species ($p < 0.05$). Meanwhile, oak and ash, at $20.5\text{‰} \pm 0.25$ SEM
363 and $20.7\text{‰} \pm 0.17$ SEM respectively, were not significantly different from each other ($p =$
364 0.768).

365 **3.4 Species differences in per-tree photosynthesis and contribution to canopy GPP**

366 Seasonal dynamics of $A_{\text{ISO/SF}}$ (per tree) and $\text{GPP}_{\text{ISO/SF}}$ (per species) varied among species (Fig.
367 4). In spring, carbon fluxes began earlier in the understory hornbeam compared to the oak and
368 ash and dominated canopy GPP until DOY 120 or so (Fig. 5). All species began to increase
369 their carbon fluxes in response to rising temperatures and foliage development, steadily
370 maintaining this upward trend until the end of April. However, the cold temperatures of April
371 and May (Fig. 1) triggered a noticeable decrease in carbon fluxes in these months, especially
372 in May (Fig. 4). All species resumed the increase in the latter part of June, reaching a peak in
373 August before a subsequent decline. Hornbeam and oak managed to sustain relatively high
374 carbon fluxes until the end of the season even though the oak and ash had leafed out above the
375 hornbeam and it showed signs of partial leaf senescence (Fig. S1). As a consequence, hornbeam

376 represented a high proportion of canopy GPP until the very end of the growing season (Fig. 5).
377 In contrast, ash rapidly declined following the initiation of leaf senescence. At the level of
378 individual trees, oak exhibited significantly higher values ($p < 0.001$) compared to hornbeam
379 and ash, which did not significantly differ ($p = 0.47$) between them (Fig. 4a). On the other hand,
380 at the level of species contribution to canopy GPP, hornbeam displayed significantly higher
381 values ($p < 0.001$), while oak and ash were not significantly different ($p = 0.24$; Fig. 4b).

382 The GPP values estimated by the EC and ISO/SF methods were in good agreement during 2021
383 (Pearson's $r = 0.76$, $p < 0.0001$), with the regression producing a significant linear fit ($R^2 =$
384 0.56 , $p < 0.0001$; Fig. 6). However, the match was better before day 212, after which the ISO/SF
385 method began to yield higher, but still correlated values compared to EC. As a consequence,
386 cumulative estimates by the ISO/SF and EC methods agreed remarkably well ($p = 0.273$) until
387 DOY 212 with totals of $1066 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and $992 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, respectively, after which the
388 $\text{GPP}_{\text{ISO/SF}}$ method overestimated relative to the GPP_{EC} method (Fig. 6). Over the whole period
389 $\text{GPP}_{\text{ISO/SF}}$ was 28% higher than GPP_{EC} , at $2071 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ vs. $1606 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, respectively.

390 **4 Discussion**

391 **4.1 $\text{GPP}_{\text{ISO/SF}}$ and GPP_{EC} method comparison**

392 Our study used a completely independent method to estimate GPP and compared it to the
393 conventional EC method. Although the ISO/SF method has been used before, ours was the first
394 that used the THB approach to measure sap flow. Also for the first time, the ISO/SF method
395 was applied to a deciduous broadleaf forest ecosystem, where dramatic phenological changes
396 might challenge the ISO/SF method. The methods yielded highly similar seasonal patterns until
397 the end of July. The ISO/SF method yielded higher, but still correlated values starting around
398 DOY 212 (July 31) and continuing to the end of the photosynthetic season; this late-season
399 discrepancy yielded higher annual totals compared to GPP_{EC} estimates (Fig. 6). Given that the
400 measurements are completely independent, yet show close agreement in the early season, this
401 improves confidence in the robustness of the methodologies during that period. At the same
402 time, the discrepancies late in the growing season raise questions about what may differ at that
403 time. In the text that follows, we first review uncertainties and limitations of each method, then
404 compare species differences and seasonal dynamics.

405 **4.2 Uncertainties and limitations**

406 **4.2.1 Eddy Covariance**

407 Canopy decoupling has been a particular concern with regard to the use of eddy covariance to
408 estimate quantitatively accurate fluxes in forests. For example, one previous study conducted
409 in a complex, multi-layered forest in Switzerland, which examined both below- and above-
410 canopy fluxes, also identified decoupling issues (Paul-Limoges et al. 2017). The study found
411 that below- and above-canopy fluxes became decoupled under full canopy closure, thus leading
412 to unaccounted for below-canopy fluxes when measured only above the canopy. This was
413 particularly important because under-canopy fluxes comprised primarily a net carbon source
414 dominated by soil respiration (Paul-Limoges et al. 2017). This pattern suggests that the EC
415 method has limitations in accurately capturing fluxes moving from the surface to the
416 atmosphere in the presence of a forest canopy. However, a previous study at our site found that
417 decoupling occurred frequently but contributed little bias to estimates of net ecosystem
418 exchange (Kowalska et al. 2022), because the floodplain is so flat that it offers no pathways for
419 advective CO₂ transport off-site. Consequently, although decoupling occurs, its primary effect
420 would be to delay the appearance of some fluxes at the height of the sensor. It would have little
421 effect on longer-term carbon budgets derived via EC at this site.

422 **4.2.2 Sap flow**

423 Our results emphasize the significant contribution of sap flow measurements to the GPP_{ISO/SF}
424 estimations, as highlighted in previous studies that have employed this approach (Hu et al.
425 2010, Klein et al. 2016). One criticism of the GPP_{ISO/SF} method is that there have been problems
426 with the calibration of sap flow data at other sites (Klein et al. 2016, Vernay et al. 2024). These
427 problems are so far mostly confined to the widely used Granier Heat-Dissipation (GHD)
428 method (Steppe et al. 2010, Vernay et al. 2024). In contrast, the sap flow measurements in our
429 study are based on the THB method (Čermák et al. 1973, 2004, Kučera et al. 1977, Sakuratani
430 1981). The THB method does not require calibration in the sense of adding empirical
431 coefficients of sapwood depth or wound coefficients (Urban et al. 2012). Notably, the THB
432 method has been used for calibration of other methods (i.e. GHD) in the field (Lundblad et al.
433 2001, Klein et al. 2014, 2016). Unlike the GHD sensor, it is not based on point temperature
434 measurements that must be scaled across the sapwood, but on heating a known volume of
435 xylem (Tatarinov et al. 2005). The value given from the measurement is not the density or
436 velocity of the flow but the mass of sap flowing in that volume (i.e., sap flow rate; Flo *et al.*,

437 2019). This direct xylem heating of the THB method renders it suitable even for large flows,
438 which may occur in species with large-diameter vessels (i.e., ring-porous angiosperms; Kučera
439 *et al.*, 2020). Such species, which include the oak and ash reported here, have shown greater
440 bias than other species when the GHD method is employed to estimate sap flow density (Yi
441 and Xu 2023). Thus, the THB method has a strong physical and mathematical basis (Tatarinov
442 *et al.* 2005), reducing one of the sources of error that arises with other methods, and was
443 necessary for the application of the ISO/SF method to these species.

444 **4.2.3 Stable isotopes and intrinsic water-use efficiency**

445 Several previous studies have used $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ to estimate iWUE. In these studies, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was
446 determined by sampling either from the foliage (Hu *et al.* 2010), from a complex mixture of
447 stemwood and foliage (Klein *et al.* 2016, Oulehle *et al.* 2023) or from phloem contents (Vernay
448 *et al.* 2020, 2024). We inferred iWUE from the isotopic composition of phloem contents. This
449 approach provides a weighted integration of whole-canopy photosynthesis, where the
450 weighting is based on net photosynthetic rates (Ubierna and Marshall 2011). Moreover, the
451 estimate is updated as phloem contents are replaced. We observed a distinct break in the
452 seasonal progression of isotopic discrimination in the phloem contents of all three species four
453 to five weeks after the new leaves appeared, perhaps as the new photosynthate was redirected
454 downward after supporting the burst of new growth after budbreak (inset, Fig. 3). After the
455 break, phloem Δ increased linearly in a way that we were unable to explain with weather data
456 (not shown). Some reports claim that the isotopic composition is modified as phloem contents
457 are mixed and transported down the tree (Offermann *et al.* 2011, Bögelein *et al.* 2019), however
458 the largest difference is between leaves and branch phloem (Bögelein *et al.*, 2019). The
459 discrepancy in GPP that arose between ISO/SF and EC after day 212 was roughly consistent
460 in direction and size with predictions from these studies, leading us to speculate that
461 downstream modification of phloem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was restricted to this late season period. If so, one
462 must be careful with the ISO/SF estimates during this time. Further studies of seasonal trends
463 in vertical phloem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ would be valuable as a test. However, even if the method is only
464 unbiased before the end of July, it is still valuable as a test of the GPP_{EC} estimates during that
465 period.

466 Some previous authors have corrected the iWUE estimates for mesophyll conductance (g_{mes}).
467 Both Klein *et al.* (2016) and Vernay *et al.* (2020) explicitly accounted for this parameter, which
468 provides a bias adjustment for the inference of iWUE from $\delta^{13}\text{C}$. In the present study, we

469 assumed that this adjustment is built into the 27‰ photosynthetic discrimination (Eq. (5);
470 Cernusak *et al.*, 2013). This assumption might miss the seasonal variation in g_{mes} , observed in
471 pine (Stangl *et al.* 2022), and we are eager to measure it in future work. We discuss its possible
472 consequences below.

473 **4.2.4 The role of understory vegetation**

474 The $GPP_{ISO/SF}$ method provides photosynthetic estimates only for the trees whose sap flow is
475 measured, whereas GPP_{EC} quantifies carbon fluxes of the entire ecosystem, introducing a
476 source of potential bias. For instance, the contribution of understory vegetation to overall
477 ecosystem exchange can be substantial, as demonstrated in previous studies (Jarosz *et al.* 2008,
478 Tian *et al.* 2021, Marshall *et al.* 2023). However, these studies reported results from relatively
479 simple, monospecific forest ecosystems with a leaf area index of 2-3 $m^2 m^{-2}$, whereas our study
480 site exhibited a higher leaf area index of 6-7.5 $m^2 m^{-2}$ during the growing season (Kowalska *et al.*
481 *et al.* 2020). Moreover, the understory contributions in the previous studies were only 6-7% of
482 total GPP (Tian *et al.*, 2021; Marshall *et al.*, 2023). At our site, as over-story leaves emerge,
483 PPFD in the understory decreased sharply (Fig. S4), reducing the light available for
484 photosynthesis. Consequently, the carbon fluxes measured by the EC tower beneath the canopy
485 were predominantly controlled by respiration, with photosynthesis by understory vegetation
486 remaining negligible (Fig. S4). Similar results were obtained in multi-layered forest in
487 Switzerland, where under-canopy fluxes were dominated by soil respiration (Paul-Limoges *et al.*
488 *et al.* 2017). Thus, at our study site, the majority of carbon flux could be attributed to the trees.
489 Although the $GPP_{ISO/SF}$ method must be downward biased by the neglect of understory
490 photosynthesis, the effect here should have been negligible.

491 **4.3 Species differences**

492 Hornbeam leafed out nearly a month earlier than the other two species (Fig. 2), allowing it to
493 maximize carbon gain before the main canopy forms (Augspurger *et al.* 2005). Additionally,
494 its leaves continued to transpire well into the end of the season, even as they yellowed, while
495 the transpiration of ash leaves gradually diminished even when they remained green (Fig. 2).
496 In fact, the hornbeam contributes a remarkably large proportion to the GPP of the whole stand
497 throughout photosynthetic period—even after the dominant oaks and ashes have leafed out
498 (Fig. 5). Although its per-tree photosynthetic rates are smaller than those of oak (Fig. 4a), its
499 high abundance more than compensates. In terms of GPP, one might well term this a hornbeam-
500 dominated forest.

501 This disparity suggests an opportunity to enhance carbon sequestration through improved
502 forest management. For instance, carefully balancing the density of hornbeam, which
503 consumes large amounts of water while producing rather little biomass (Szatniewska et al.,
504 2022) could more effectively allocate soil moisture resources among oaks and ashes, perhaps
505 enhancing carbon sequestration and forest productivity (Fig. 4a).

506 **5. Conclusions**

507 In this multi-species forest, the two methods, isotope/sap flow and eddy covariance, agreed
508 well in their canopy photosynthesis (GPP) estimates from late spring until late July. The
509 isotopic estimates of intrinsic water-use efficiency varied less over the growing season than the
510 sap flux estimates, which rose from essentially zero as the leaves emerged. The THB method
511 for measuring sap flow required no calibration to achieve this agreement across all species,
512 improving upon the thermal dissipation estimates that have previously been used for this
513 approach to estimating GPP. More work is required on the extent to which phloem contents
514 reflect canopy photosynthesis, but this work should be focused on the latter part of the growing
515 season. Hornbeam was by far the dominant contributor to canopy GPP throughout the growing
516 season, which is somewhat surprising considering its subordinate position in the canopy.

517 **Data availability**

518 Data that support the findings of this study will be made available upon request.

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527 **Conflict of interests**

528 None declared.

529 **Authors' contributions**

530 J.D.M., M.S. and G.J. contributed to the study conception and design; M.S., G.J., N.K., I.Z.,
531 J.S., O.U., J.Č., P.H., M.A., and M.P. contributed to experiment execution and data collection;
532 M.S., J.D.M., and G.J., contributed to data analysis and interpretation; M.S., and J.D.M. wrote
533 and edited the original draft. All authors read, reviewed, and approved the final manuscript.

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785 **List of Figures**

786 **Figure 1.** Weather at the Lanžhot site in 2021. (a) daily mean (solid black line), maximum (red
787 band) and minimum (blue band) air temperature (T ; °C), (b) daytime vapor pressure deficit
788 (VPDD; hPa) and relative air humidity (RH; %), (c) daily soil water content (SWC; %) with
789 grey band indicating standard error of mean among sensors and (d) daily precipitation sums (P ;
790 mm).

791 **Figure 2.** Seasonal dynamics of leaf phenological phases and sap flow in hornbeam (green),
792 oak (red) and ash (blue) during 2021 vegetative season. BB = budbreak, FF 10–100% = foliage
793 formation, FDLA = fully developed leaf area, LC 10–100% = leaf coloring, LF 10–100% =
794 leaf fall. Whiskers and colored bands are standard deviations of leaf phenological observations
795 ($n = 7$ per species) and sap flow ($n = 5$ per species), respectively.

796 **Figure 3.** Stable carbon isotope composition of phloem contents ($\delta^{13}C_p$) in hornbeam (green),
797 oak (red) and ash (blue) during 2021 vegetative season. Bands indicate the standard error of
798 the mean ($n = 5$ per species). Inset figures represent the variation of observed carbon
799 discrimination (Δ ; ‰), which adjusts $\delta^{13}C_p$ for seasonal variation in $\delta^{13}C$ of the atmosphere.
800 Bands indicate a 95% confidence interval of linear regression. Red squares on the inset graphs
801 highlight data collected during and just after foliage expansion (see Methods for details).
802 Dashed lines within the inset graphs indicate full leafout (FF 100%), with bands representing
803 the standard deviations.

804 **Figure 4.** (a) Daily photosynthesis rate ($A_{ISO/SF}$; g C tree⁻¹ day⁻¹) and (b) scaled up gross
805 primary production ($GPP_{ISO/SF}$; g C m⁻² day⁻¹) in hornbeam (green), oak (red) and ash (blue)
806 during 2021 vegetative season. Color bands denote the standard error of mean ($n = 5$). Inset
807 boxplots illustrate the distribution of mean daily $A_{ISO/SF}$ and $GPP_{ISO/SF}$ across the species, with
808 letters indicating significantly distinguishable species.

809 **Figure 5.** Proportional contribution of each species to daily canopy GPP, where canopy GPP
810 was estimated as the daily sum of $GPP_{ISO/SF}$ over the three tree species. In the graph, green
811 represents hornbeam, red oak, and blue ash.

812 **Figure 6.** Daily estimations of GPP_{EC} (solid red), $GPP_{ISO/SF}$ (dashed dark grey). Inset chart
813 compares daily estimates of GPP by eddy covariance and phloem isotope/sap flow methods.
814 The statistics displayed within the inset graph apply to the entire observed period. The blue

815 dots represent the period prior to day 212 ($R^2 = 0.85$), while the red dots denote the period
816 afterward ($R^2 = 0.60$).

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888 Figure 6